

A NEW EQUATION FOR STRONG ELECTROLYTES. PART I

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An equation for uni-univalent strong electrolytes has been derived.

Assuming the concept of ion atmosphere and the validity of Poisson's equation as put forward by Debye and Hückel (*Physikal. Z.*, 1923, **24**, 185) an equation, which has been found to be valid in a few test cases up to 4*N*, has been derived for uni-univalent strong electrolytes. The equation has been derived on the basis of two hypotheses :

(i) The total number of particles, *i.e.* the sum of the positive and negative ions, per unit volume remains constant.

(ii) The number of positive and negative ions per unit volume around a central ion would then be given not by Boltzmann's distribution* but by a distribution of the type

$$n_+ = \frac{\sum_i n_i z_i}{e^{\psi/kT} + 1}$$

$$n_- = \frac{\sum_i n_i}{e^{-\psi/kT} + 1} \quad \dots (1)$$

where $\sum_i n_i$ is the total number of particles, *i.e.* sum of all the ions present, per unit volume ;

n_+ and n_- are the numbers of positive and negative ions per unit volume ;

e is the electronic charge ;

k is the Boltzmann's constant ;

T is the absolute temperature ;

ψ is the potential at any point due to all the ions present with respect to a particular central ion.

* The condition that the total number of ions per unit volume should remain the same could be arrived at from a modified Boltzmann's distribution of the type,

$$n_+ = A e^{-\psi/kT} \quad \text{and} \quad n_- = A e^{\psi/kT} \quad \dots (1a)$$

$$\text{where } A = \frac{\sum_i n_i}{e^{-\psi/kT} + e^{\psi/kT}} \quad \dots (1b)$$

Poisson's equation would then assume the form

$$\nabla^2 \lambda = K^2 \tan \lambda$$

$$\text{where } \lambda = \psi/kT \quad \text{and} \quad K^2 = \frac{4\pi e^2 \sum_i n_i}{DkT}$$

But the author has found that the values of activity coefficients of electrolytes calculated by using this formula do not agree with those obtained experimentally.

The charge density

$$\begin{aligned} \rho &= (n_+ - n_-)e \\ &= \sum_i n_i e \tan h \frac{e\psi}{2kT} \end{aligned} \quad \dots (2)$$

It will be seen that ρ remains finite even when $\psi \rightarrow \infty$

Poisson's equation would then assume the form

$$\nabla^2 \psi = \frac{4\pi \sum_i n_i e}{D} \tan h \frac{e\psi}{2kT} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\text{or} \quad \nabla^2 \lambda = K^2 \tanh \lambda \quad \dots (4)$$

where, $D =$ the dielectric constant of the medium

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda &= \frac{e\psi}{2kT} \\ K^2 &= \frac{2\pi e^2 \sum_i n_i}{DkT} \end{aligned} \quad \dots (5)$$

In order to solve the equation (4) it has been separated into two parts

$$\nabla^2 \lambda = K^2 \lambda \text{ for small values of } \lambda \quad \dots (6)$$

$$\text{and} \quad \nabla^2 \lambda = K^2 \quad \text{for large values of } \lambda \quad \dots (7)$$

$$\text{or} \quad \frac{1}{\xi^2} \cdot \frac{d}{d\xi} \left(\xi^2 \frac{d\lambda}{d\xi} \right) = \lambda \quad \dots (6a)$$

$$\text{and} \quad \frac{1}{\xi^2} \cdot \frac{d}{d\xi} \left(\xi^2 \frac{d\lambda}{d\xi} \right) = 1 \quad \dots (7a)$$

where $\xi = K r$

With the boundary condition that λ tends to 0 as $\xi \rightarrow \infty$ Eqn (6a) gives

$$\lambda = \frac{B e^{-\xi}}{\xi} \quad \dots (8)$$

and solving Eqn. (7a) we get

$$\lambda = \frac{\xi^2}{6} + c + \frac{H}{\xi} \quad \dots (9)$$

where B , C and H are constants of integration to be determined.

In order to find out C and H , the two curves given by the equation (8) and (9) are fitted at the point ξ_1 where λ is equal to 1, for if at this point $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2$

$$\text{and} \quad \frac{d\lambda_1}{d\xi} = \frac{d\lambda_2}{d\xi} \text{ then } \frac{d^2\lambda_1}{d\xi^2} \text{ would be equal to } \frac{d^2\lambda_2}{d\xi^2}$$

where λ_1 and λ_2 are the values of λ for the equations (8) and (9) respectively

Thus we get

$$H = \frac{\xi_1^3}{3} + \xi_1^2 + \xi_1 \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

$$C = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 - (\xi_1 + 1)^2 \right] \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

Now, in order to find out H and therefore ξ_1 and C we assume the continuity of normal induction on the surface of the ion. It is obvious that Eqn. (8) is valid in the neighbourhood of infinity and Eqn. (9) in the neighbourhood of zero. Hence using Eqn. (9) we get

$$H = \frac{e^2 K}{2DkT} + \frac{K^2 a_1^2}{3} \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

where a_1 is the effective ionic radius of the central ion.

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_1 &= (1 + 3H)^{1/2} - 1 \\ &= \left(1 + \frac{3e^2 K}{2DkT} + K^2 a_1^2 \right)^{1/2} - 1 \quad \dots \quad (12a) \end{aligned}$$

$$= (1 + g)^{1/2} - 1 \quad \dots \quad (12b)$$

$$\text{where } g = \frac{3e^2 K}{2DkT} + K^2 a_1^2 \quad \dots \quad (12c)$$

$$\text{and } C = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 - (1 + g)^{3/2} \right] \quad \dots \quad (13)$$

Hence ψ_0 , the potential due to the ion atmosphere on the surface of the central ion is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_0 &= \psi_{a_1} - \frac{e}{Da_1} \\ &= \frac{kT}{e} \cdot K^2 a_1^2 + \frac{kT}{e} \left[1 - (1 + g)^{3/2} \right] \quad \dots \quad (14) \end{aligned}$$

Now, following Debye (*Physikal. Z.*, 1924, 28, 97) we can calculate the maximum work due to electrostatic forces (short range interactions, e.g. forces of polarisation, etc., have been neglected) which would give the difference between the thermodynamic potential of the real solution and the ideal solution

$$\begin{aligned} \text{This work } W &= \int_0^1 e\psi_{0,x} dx : \\ &= kT \cdot K^2 a_1^2 \int_0^1 x dx + kT \int_0^1 \frac{1 - (1 + gx^2)^{3/2}}{x} dx \\ &= \frac{1}{2} kT K^2 a_1^2 + kT P + kT Q(g) \quad (15) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{where } P = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \tan^{-1} \sqrt{3} - \frac{1}{2} \ln 3$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(g) = & \frac{1}{2} \ln \left\{ (1+g)^{2/3} + (1+g)^{1/3} + 1 \right\} \\ & - \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \tan^{-1} \frac{2(1+g)^{1/3} + 1}{\sqrt{3}} - \frac{g^2}{2} (1+g)^{2/3} \end{aligned} \quad \dots (15a)$$

$$\text{Hence the total work } \bar{W} = \sum_i n_i W \quad \dots (16)$$

and the activity coefficient f_i of the ion, by definition, is given by the equation

$$\begin{aligned} \ln f_i = & \frac{1}{kT} \frac{\delta W}{\delta n_i} \\ = & K^2 a_i^2 + P + \phi(g) + \sum_i n_i \frac{\delta \phi}{\delta n_i} \end{aligned} \quad \dots (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{where } \sum_i n_i \frac{\delta \phi}{\delta n_i} = & \frac{1}{2} \frac{\frac{e^2 K}{2DkT} + K^3 a_i^2}{(1+g)^{1/3}} + \frac{\frac{e^2 K}{2DkT} + K^3 a_i^2}{2(1+g)^{2/3}} \\ & - \frac{e^2 K / 2DkT + K^3 a_i^2}{3(1+g)^{2/3} \{1 + \frac{1}{3} [2(1+g)^{1/3} + 1]^2\}} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{e^2 K / 2DkT + K^3 a_i^2}{(1+g)^{1/3}} \end{aligned} \quad (17a)$$

The mean activity coefficient of the electrolyte is therefore given by

$$\ln f_{\pm} = \frac{\ln f_+ + \ln f_-}{2} \quad \dots (18)$$

Table I gives the mean activity coefficients of CsCl and KCl in the *molar scale of concentration* (*g. moles per litre of solution*) calculated from the formulae (17 and 18) and using the following ionic radii, $\text{Cs}^+ = 1.67 \text{ \AA}$, $\text{K}^+ = 1.33 \text{ \AA}$ and $\text{Cl}^- = 1.81 \text{ \AA}$, as given by crystallographic data and the dielectric constant of water.

TABLE I

Mean activity coefficients at 25°.

	0.01N.	1.0N.	4.0N.
CsCl	0.9239	0.5702	0.4466
KCl	0.9237	0.5581	0.4163
		0.6209*	0.5667*

* The values are for KCl when the ionic radius of K^+ is taken as 2.76 $\text{\AA}$.

Table II gives the observed data of mean activity coefficients at 25° in *molar scale of concentration* (*g. moles per 1000 g. of solvent*). The values for molar scale would be slightly less.

TABLE II

Mean activity coefficients $f_{\pm}$ at 25° in molal scale of concentration.

	0.01M.	1.0M.	4.0M.
KCl	0.922†	0.634†	0.582‡
		0.605‡	
CsCl		0.543‡	0.474‡

† Falkenhagen, "Electrolytes," Oxford University Press, 1939, pp. 65, 67.

‡ Harned & Owen, "The Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions", Reinhold Publishing Corp., 1943, p. 562.

It will be seen that for CsCl the calculated values given in Table I agree well with the observed data. The low values for KCl at higher concentrations are due to the hydration of K^+ ions. If we consider the K^+ ion packed within a layer of water molecules of diameter 2.76 Å and use 2.76 Å as the effective ionic radius for the K^+ ion, the values for the activity coefficients of KCl for 1*N* and 4*N* become respectively 0.6209 and 0.5667 which show satisfactory agreement with the observed values.

The equation also explains how at higher concentrations the activity coefficients may become greater than unity.

It will be noted that here the ions have been assumed to be spherically symmetrical. The equation (17) therefore will not be valid for spherically unsymmetrical ions like NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} or for rod shaped particles of long chain compounds and colloidal electrolytes.

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